

MOBIDATALAB

Labs for prototyping future mobility data sharing solutions in the cloud

| D6.1 Dissemination Report

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Summary sheet

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Abstract	This document defines the dissemination and communication strategy for the MobiDataLab project

Legal Disclaimer

MOBIDATALAB (Grant Agreement No 101006879) is a Research and Innovation Actions project funded by the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020. This document contains information on MOBIDATALAB core activities, findings, and outcomes. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the MOBIDATALAB consortium and cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission.

Project partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
POLIS Network	Belgium	POLIS
F6S	Ireland	F6S
AKKA	France	AKKA
ICOOR	Italy	ICOOR

Document history

Version	Date	Organisation	Main area of changes	Comments
V0.1	27.04.2021	POLIS, F6S, AKKA	all	Draft for Review
V0.2	11.05.2021	ICOOR	all	Review
V0.3	28.05.2021	POLIS	all	Rework
V0.4	31.05.2021	AKKA	all	Quality Check
V1.0	31.05.2021	AKKA		Final version

Executive Summary

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy is the project's guidance document for all dissemination and communication activities that will take place within the project. It should be seen as a living document that will be adapted and revised throughout the project and following the timeline provided in the document.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan identifies and describes the target groups for dissemination activities and explains how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It describes the main dissemination tools, which will be particularly important for outreach activities.

This strategy also identifies key initiatives and EU-funded projects to establish strategic alliances and collaboration mechanisms and defines the methodology for the establishment of the external interest groups that will play an important role in the transferability of the obtained results.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
WP	Work Package

Content

Introduction

1.1. About MobiDataLab

There has been an explosion of mobility services and data sharing in recent years. Building on this, the EU-funded MobiDataLab project works to foster the sharing of data amongst transport authorities, operators and other mobility stakeholders in Europe. MobiDataLab develops knowledge as well as a cloud solution aimed at easing the sharing of data. Specifically, the project is based on a continuous co-development of knowledge and technical solutions. It collects and analyses the advice and recommendations of experts and supporting cities, regions, clusters and associations. These actions are assisted by the incremental construction of a cross-thematic knowledge base and a cloud-based service platform, which will improve access and usage of data sharing resources.

1.2. About the MobiDataLab Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The Dissemination and Communication plan guides the dissemination activities within MobiDataLab. It identifies and describes the target groups for dissemination activities and explains how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It also describes the main dissemination tools to be developed within the project and identifies project milestones that will be particularly important to link outreach activities too. The plan also lists relevant events on national, European and international levels and specialised scientific journals and publications to publish the project results. The project will take advantage of the strong networks that the partners possess in order to disseminate widely.

1.3. Intended audience & Review process

The dissemination level of this deliverable is 'public' (PU) but it is mainly addressed to the whole MobiDataLab consortium. While all the partners are responsible for implementing the Dissemination and Communication plan, POLIS in collaboration with the project coordinator AKKA and other partners (F6S and HOVE) will be the main responsables for the implementation of the strategy.

It is important to note that this deliverable should be considered as a living document that will be adapted throughout the lifetime of the project. This will be done after two official reporting periods. An overview of the planned revision is presented in the table below:

Table 1 Planned revision of the deliverable 6.1

D6.1 developed and submitted	M4
Revision 1	M16-M18
Revision 2	M26-M28

Besides planned revisions, changes will be introduced to the document in case the need arises at any time of the project.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

The dissemination strategy first presents target groups of the project and its specific messages, and communication channels to reach out to them. It then describes the project's visual identity and the templates created for a harmonised communication, as well as the purpose of each of these elements. The strategy details all the material for communication and dissemination, i.e., leaflet, video, etc., and the online tools to widen the project's outreach (social media, website, etc.). Finally, it exposes how it will build a community to foster cross-fertilisation of its results and other related works, before explaining how the dissemination impact will be assessed and monitored.

The strategy should support other WPs in increasing their outreach and therefore the impact of their outcomes in the wider society. It also provides basic design guidelines for deliverables and other produced material. It relies on the project's objectives in terms of exploitation and community-building, as well as the planned events and activities in each WPs.

2.

Target groups and communication

2.1. Key Message and Project Mission Statement

The key message of the project is that MobiDataLab will support the change towards a new mobility paradigm by proposing a methodology and tools that foster the development of a data-sharing culture in Europe and beyond. This mission statement consists of five specific objectives:

- To make a comprehensive inventory and assessment of mechanisms enhancing data sharing in the transport sector;
- To identify relevant use cases and define new requirements improving the discovery, accessibility, interoperability and usability of transport data;
- To obtain a clear understanding of the potential of digitalisation and data sharing;
- To prototype a scalable cloud solution for sharing transport data, showcasing the most effective means to facilitate access to and exchange of mobility data;

- To gather representative of data providers and data consumers and conduct agile exchange sessions aiming to co-create, explore, experiment and evaluate the Transport Cloud.

To create an impact, these advancements in the data-sharing culture will be widely communicated in targeted messages described in the following section.

2.2. Target Groups

The project dissemination and impact creation aims at targeting the following groups that are directly involved and concerned by the project results:

- **General Public/Press:** the aim is to improve their understanding of data sharing challenges, opportunities and most appropriate use cases.
- **Research and Scientific Communities:** the aim is to integrate the latest R&D knowledge into the project and thus bringing the project's results far beyond the state of the art and ensuring future exploitation/development.
- **Local/Transport Authorities:** the communication will be targeted at improving their understanding of the potential for data sharing and encouraging them to take inspiration from good practice examples and tools.
- **Cluster and Network Associations:** the aim is to improve their understanding of data sharing challenges, opportunities and most appropriate use cases.
- **Standardisation and Certification bodies:** the aim is to communicate with national & international standardisation / certification to enable easy usability and recognition.
- **Data tech start-ups, entrepreneurs and SMEs:** the aim is to co-create innovative data-driven concepts, solutions with the potential to develop new business, partnerships and value to end-users.

Table 2 Target groups and communication activities gives an overview of the channels, activities and frequency of communication to achieve the presented outcomes:

Table 2 Target groups and communication activities

Target Group	Dissemination Channels	Activities	Frequency
General Public/Press	Social Media, Website, media channels, informational events, Newsletter, Leaflet	Articles in newspapers/daily magazines, presentations at events, social media posts, website news items, press releases.	Constant communication during the project period, specially when reaching project milestones.
Research and Academic Communities	Scientific Journals, Social Media, Website, scientific conferences, fairs, Newsletter, Leaflet	Publications in Scientific journals, training sessions, presentations at workshops, webinars and other events, website news items, social	Constant communication during the project period, specially when reaching project milestones.

		media posts, Living Lab participation.	
Local/Transport Authorities	Direct contact through POLIS, Social Media, Website, Stakeholder group meetings, Newsletter and final event	Presentations at workshops, webinars and other events, website news items, social media posts, publications, factsheets, Living Lab participation	Constant communication during the project period, specially when reaching project milestones.
Clusters, Network associations (incl. data sharing ecosystem)	Stakeholder group meetings, webinars, workshops, newsletter and final event	Presentations at workshops, webinars and other events, website news items, social media posts, publications, factsheets, Living Lab participation	Constant communication during the project period, specially when reaching project milestones.
Standardisation and certification bodies	Direct contact through relevant consortium members (specially POLIS), Website, Social Media	Presentations at workshops, webinars and other events, publications, factsheets, Website News Items, Social Media posts	To be defined once Virtual and Living Labs have delivered results
Data tech entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs	F6S platform, Social media, entrepreneurial events, Datathons/Hackathons/Codagons	Website News Items, Social Media posts, presentations at workshops, webinars and other events, Living Lab participation	To be defined once Data Providers have defined challenges; Anticipating of a MobiDataLab event or activity important for these stakeholders

2.3. Stakeholder Database

A contact list of relevant stakeholders at local, regional, national and international levels is crucial to provide partners with easy methods of dissemination of all project outputs to the relevant target groups. Similarly, MobiDataLab will utilise all relevant international contacts available to the consortium partners to promote the project at local, regional, national and European levels.

A MobiDataLab contact database will be developed in the first year of the project and kept updated. This database will be part of the project's lasting legacy, as it will allow stakeholders to have a point of reference that can be enriched and updated for future MobiDataLab-related activities.

Project identity and templates

3.1. Project Identity

3.

MobiDataLab will develop a distinctive and modern visual identity, which will run through all the project dissemination activities and across all channels and dissemination platforms. These professionally designed materials will support the project's presence at conferences and exhibitions, making it clearly identifiable. The visual identity will include the following elements: a branding charter detailing elements of the visual identity, the project logo, information on the logo size and use, colours to represent the project, instructions on incorrect uses of the logo, and fonts.

3.1.1. Brand

The MobiDataLab Brand will support the public recognition of the project as a trusted source and voice on the topic of mobility data sharing. It will enable to identify contributions of the project to works and events on the topic. It is composed of a logo, colours, fonts and sizes which are representative of the project's identity. The brand is described in a branding charter, which is a PDF document showing the logo, colours, fonts and sizes, and giving instructions on how to use them.

3.1.2. Project Logo

The MobiDataLab logo is composed of the word MOBIDATALAB in three shades of blue, with a baseline in black: "Labs for prototyping future mobility data sharing solutions in the cloud".

MOBIDATALAB
Labs for prototyping future mobility data sharing solutions in the cloud

A square version is also developed for social media, web and other potential uses:

**MOBI
DATA
LAB**

3.1.3. Logo size and use

There are no predetermined sizes for the MOBIDATALAB logo. Scale should be determined by the available space, aesthetics, function and visibility. There is no preset maximum size for the MOBIDATALAB logo. Minimum size is as shown in the branding charter document.

The logo is to be used on all MOBIDATALAB communication media. The MOBIDATALAB logo should always be surrounded by a minimum area of space. A clear space around the logo is recommended to maintain visual clarity. The recommended clear space will be detailed in the charter.

3.1.4. Colours

The colours used for the MOBIDATALAB logo are different shades of blue, as follows:

- MOBI color (Hexa) = 42688b
- DATA color (Hexa) = 5e8ab4
- LAB color (Hexa) = 70bbf0

The baseline is in black, color (Hexa) = 252525.

Figure 1 MobiDataLab Guidance Book 2021 - Colours

MOBI colour	DATA colour	LAB colour	BASELINE colour
<p>DARK BLUE</p> <p>#42688B</p> <p>C: 78 R: 66 M: 52 G: 104 Y: 27 B: 139 K: 11</p>	<p>MEDIUM BLUE</p> <p>#5E8AB4</p> <p>C: 67 R: 94 M: 38 G: 138 Y: 14 B: 180 K: 2</p>	<p>LIGHT BLUE</p> <p>#70BBF0</p> <p>C: 56 R: 112 M: 13 G: 187 Y: 0 B: 240 K: 0</p>	<p>DARK GREY</p> <p>#252525</p> <p>C: 73 R: 37 M: 63 G: 37 Y: 59 B: 37 K: 75</p>

3.1.5. Incorrect use

The MOBIDATALAB logo must not be altered or modified in any way. It should never be stretched or skewed out of proportion, used with other colours than the above-mentioned predefined colours, without a clear space around it, or with another orientation than the original one.

3.1.6. Fonts

The Arial Heavy typeface is to be used for all main headlines in all official MOBIDATALAB print and online communication media. The Arial typeface is the primary typeface for all running texts. The font sizes for the MOBIDATALAB logo are 267px for the main letters, and 40px for the baseline letters.

3.2. Document templates

Templates for Word and PPT documents of the project will be developed, to ensure the harmonisation of all produced documents. These templates can be used for all project's related documents (deliverables, agendas, minutes, slide show presentations, etc.). Specific attention will be paid to propose "easy to use" tools, providing automatic table of content for example, and automatically formatting the content accordingly.

3.3. Visual Identity Notices/Disclaimer

As the project is funded by the European Union, dissemination, communication and publication materials must clearly acknowledge the receipt of EU funding through:

- The display of the EU flag;
- The following text referring to Horizon2020: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006879".

A disclaimer will also be included on the website, stating:

"MobiDataLab is funded by the EU under the H2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant agreement No 101006879). The content of this website reflects solely the views of its authors. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The MobiDataLab consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind that may result from the use of these materials."

Any publication or any other material prepared by the consortium members, even if at national level, on behalf of MobiDataLab and in the framework of their assigned tasks in the project, shall at least display the project logo and EU flag and funding statement.

Dissemination and communication material

4.1. Project leaflet and Final Brochure

4.

An initial leaflet will be produced during the first year of the project. The leaflet will introduce MobiDataLab and its key objectives while following the project's visual and branding guidelines. It will serve as a promotion tool during conferences and events and will be made available online for download. Each consortium member will be provided with a defined number of leaflets depending on their requirements (expected event attendance or other distribution needs).

A final brochure will be produced at the end of the project. The brochure will present the outcomes and results of the project while following the project's visual and branding guidelines.

4.2. Technical leaflet and posters

Technical leaflets for each living lab will be produced and distributed at a later stage to present the project's technology, use cases and results. Additionally, technical posters will be created as needed for events.

4.3. Video

Two short promotional videos will be produced halfway through the project, when more tangible progresses are available. The videos will present the project, highlighting the Living Labs, and its services. The videos will also be published on partners' websites and will be used for project presentations at public conferences and workshops. The first video will be produced during year 2 of the project and the second video will be produced during year 3.

4.4. Press Releases

At important project milestones, press releases will be issued and published and, when relevant, sent to European and national press. A standard press release template has been created, which can then be adapted to each partner.

The first press release was published during the Kick-Off meeting of the project.

Online media

5.1. MobiDataLab Website

5.

The MobiDataLab website will be the main repository for the project outputs and resources and will offer a primary access point for interested stakeholders from the industry and the general audience. The project will also use the website to publicise its activities and events. MobiDataLab's public deliverables will be made available on the website. Analytics will be made available every 6 months to analyse the readability of the website (engagement, most visited pages, demographics) and take corrective actions if needed.

5.2. MobiDataLab Newsletter

At least once a year, electronic newsletters will be issued to ensure a regular flow of information to all interested stakeholders. A newsletter subscription form will also be added to the project website.

All partners are invited to make contributions for content to the newsletter. F6S will manage the publication of the newsletter and will organize the collection of content from partners. For that, a mailchimp account will be created.

Newsletters will be one of the main engaging tools for MobiDataLab. Newsletters will be advertised on the website and the project's social media platforms. Such communication tool will follow the project's branding guidelines and will be GDPR compliant (users will have to actively opt-in or opt-out in order to subscribe/unsubscribe from MobiDataLab's news and their data will be stored for a specific amount of time). Newsletters will be issued once per year (4 in total). In the case of the generation of more content, more newsletters can be foreseen. Such tool will also be useful to monitor the project's trend and readership behaviour and adjust the communication accordingly.

Additionally, partners are encouraged to share MobiDataLab's news and newsletter subscription form through their own organisation newsletters, especially POLIS. POLIS will include at least 3 articles/year in their newsletter during the first two years of the project, and at least 5 articles during the third year.

5.3. Social Media

Following the H2020 social media guidelines¹, key social media platforms will be used to raise the visibility of the project and engage with both professional communities and the general public. Consortium partners will employ Twitter and LinkedIn to broadcast, network and generally to inform the audience about MobiDataLab's results, successes, events, webinars, workshops, etc. When appropriate, new accounts might be created, for instance a Youtube channel to share the project promotional videos and webinars.

5.3.1. Twitter

A Twitter profile has been set up following the project's visual identity and identifying the most influential hashtags in the field of transport and data sharing. Twitter will play a key role in supporting the communications objectives of MobiDataLab. The Twitter account will be used to raise awareness for the project and showcase MobiDataLab activities and events. The language of the account will be English.

The Twitter account audience will be general public, press, other EU projects, Data tech community, European institutions, stakeholders and various professionals. The idea behind this channel is to reach a large number of followers from different backgrounds interested in the project and in charging solutions, electromobility and sustainable transport in Europe.

Tweets will contain:

- Latest news from the project;
- Activities from meetings or workshops;
- Information about upcoming events organised by MobiDataLab or where MobiDataLab will be featured (conferences, webinars, cooperation initiatives);
- Retweets of related twitter accounts of initiatives, partners, cities, projects and events.

POLIS will manage the project's Twitter account and will ensure to update content in a regular basis. Nevertheless, all partners are expected to send relevant content for Twitter and support the promotion of MobiDataLab social media accounts by sharing, liking and retweeting.

The administrator of the account will be also committed to follow and be followed by relevant audience (e.g. partners social media accounts, EU stakeholders, relevant EU projects, EU institutions, scientific research organisations etc.).

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

Main keywords and hashtags (such as #DataSharing, #Opendata, #Mobilitydata, #transport, #data, #datathon #H2020transport) will also be used in order to increase the tweets' visibility. The commission relevant accounts (@cinea_eu, @EU_H2020) will be tagged to expand the project's audience.

The tweets will contain audiovisual elements (photos, videos) if it fits more effectively to the post content. All the project posts and tweets will be automatically published on the website's home page through a social stream.

The MobiDataLab Twitter account is @MobiDataLab and can be found here: <https://twitter.com/MobiDataLab>.

5.3.2. *Linkedin*

A LinkedIn company page has also been set up following the project's visual identity and will communicate and engage with users by regularly posting content. LinkedIn will play an important role in disseminating information on the project in professional networks. The LinkedIn account will allow a large group of stakeholders but also end users to interact with the project and follow up on MobiDataLab developments, serving at the same time as a tool for the dissemination of activities and events.

The LinkedIn page will be public, rather than a private group, and it will be managed by POLIS who will ensure that posts will be published regularly. All partners will provide suggestions for content.

The main purposes of MobiDataLab posts on the project LinkedIn page are the following:

- Spread information about the project and the current activities;
- Maintain a professional and up-to-date profile;
- Share and promote interesting scientific and industrial developments and events to the community;
- Liaise with other projects and initiatives.

The main language will be English.

The MobiDataLab LinkedIn profile can be found at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/mobidatalab>.

Both social media platforms will allow the project to gather statistics (outreach, followers, likes, etc) in specific periods of time and to serve as reflector of the website: the information published on MobiDataLab's website can be shared on these two social media platforms, amplifying the outreach. In addition, both social media platforms will engage with the project's consortium and identified groups of stakeholders by following and mentioning them, maximising the project's visibility and outreach.

Community building and cross-fertilisation

6.1. Advisory Board

6.

MobiDataLab is establishing an Advisory Board aiming to provide guidance to the consortium at various stages during the three years of the project. Its main role is to provide specific advice and strategic orientations in order to guide the developments of the project, especially for the development of the Open Knowledge Base and of the Transport Cloud through the identification of resources and elicitation of innovative use cases. The members of the Advisory Board will be invited by the project to join General Assemblies for a specific workshop once a year.

At the time of the writing, eight individual experts have joined the Advisory Board and will contribute to the first version of the Open Knowledge Base. The advisors come from organisations and projects related to the transport and the data sharing ecosystem – namely Mobility Data², UITP³, the MaaS Alliance⁴, the ARCADE⁵ project, La Fabrique des Mobilités⁶, Armis ITS, Catalan Data Protection Authority. The areas of expertise of the different experts and the topics cover data governance, standards, legal, data protection, technical solutions, use cases, business models, etc. The Advisory Board will remain open to other candidate experts, and some individual experts from the CER⁷, IRF⁸ and CARA⁹ are expected to join following the letter of support they provided during the proposal writing stage.

A specific deliverable (D1.7 “report on expert committee activities” due at M36) is dedicated to the detailed description of the Advisory Board and its interactions with the consortium experts, including results of the working meetings during the whole project.

6.2. Reference Group

MobiDataLab is establishing a Reference Group designed to validate project results and help co-create, explore, experiment, and evaluate the Transport Cloud. Specifically, the MobiDataLab Reference Group will:

² Mobility Data <https://mobilitydata.org/>

³ UITP International Association of Public Transport <https://www.uitp.org/>

⁴ MaaS Alliance <https://maas-alliance.eu/>

⁵ ARCADE Aligning Research & Innovation for Connected and Automated Driving in Europe <https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/>

⁶ La Fabrique des Mobilités <https://lafabriquedesmobilites.fr/>

⁷ CER Community of European Railway <https://www.cer.be/>

⁸ IRF International Road Federation <https://www.irf.global/>

⁹ CARA European Cluster for Mobility Solutions <https://www.cara.eu/en/>

- Provide challenges for the Living Labs corresponding to concrete mobility problems: these typical problems are related to parking, public transport, road traffic, new mobility, etc. (e.g. accessibility to large events (sport, concerts, other) or touristic areas, accessibility to critical infrastructures (hospitals), etc).
- Participate to the Living Labs: these challenges will then be proposed to a community of innovators and data users, involved in dedicated hackathons/datathons. Reference Group members will participate in co-creation activities, providing challenges and answering participants' questions.
- Validate project results and provide customised feedback.

POLIS will lead in the coordination and management of the group, with support from AKKA.

6.2.1. Reference Group Members

The Reference Group consists of 15-20 relevant mobility stakeholders (i.e. local/regional authorities, transport authorities, transport associations/clusters). In accordance with their interest and priorities, the members of the Reference Group will be invited to the different MobiDataLab activities.

At the proposal stage, the following groups stakeholder were interested in participating:

- Community of European Railway (CER);
- International Road Federation (IRF);
- International Association of Public Transport (UITP);
- CARA;
- La Fabrique des Mobilités;
- Le Village by CA Toulouse 31;
- Brussels Intercommunal Transport Company (STIB- MIVB);
- AMAT Milano;
- Promalaga;
- e-Trikala;
- Municipality of Eindhoven;
- City of Roma / Municipio IX;
- Politecnico di Bari.

An open call was launched in M2 of the project on MobiDataLab's website and social media and disseminated through POLIS website, social media and newsletter. An invitation was sent to those organisations that had sent letters of support at the proposal stage. The Table 3 gives an overview of the applications to the MobiDataLab Reference Group:

Table 3 Applicants to the MobiDataLab Reference Group

Name of the City/Organisation	Type of Organisation
Benelux/NRW living lab for MaaS	International collaboration including all of the above
NaviParking	Private sector (smart parking company)
Cubic Transportation Systems	Transportation Technology Provider
BearingPoint	Management consultant (urban logistics / mobility)
Vila Velha University	Transportation professor
City Hall of Timisoara	Local Authority
Municipalitie of Eindhoven	Local Authority
Factual	Leader of the EU funded H2020 Molière project
Leuven	Local Authority
Promálaga	Local Authority
Promálaga	Local Authority
Municipality IX EUR of the City of Rome	Local Authority
Rome Mobility Agency	Local Authority
TIER Mobility	Micro-mobility operator
Nahverkehrsgesellschaft Baden-Württemberg mbH (- Mobility agency for the state of Baden-Württemberg)	Mobility Agency
New York State Department of Transportation	Transport Authority
Populus	Private sector
e-trikala SA	Municipal Company
Hamburger Hochbahn AG	Public Transportation Company
TravelAi	Transport Behaviour Data Generator

The final selection was made based on the following criteria included in the application:

- Type of organisation;
- Expected contribution.

The organisations shaded in Grey in the table were accepted as Reference Group members whereas the rest were included in MobiDataLab's Stakeholder database to be considered in future MobiDataLab activities.

6.2.2. Activity Plan for Reference Group

During the course of the project, the Reference Group will be invited to participate in at least 2 workshops and the living/virtual labs. The location and period of the activities will be fully aligned with the living labs in WP5. Reference Group members will be invited to host Living Labs activities, therefore their location will be decided later on in the project. The Table 4 summarises the initial Reference Group activity plan:

Table 4 MobiDataLab Reference Group preliminary activity plan

Type of Activity	Location	Period (subject to changes)	Aim
Results Validation Workshop	Virtual	M9-11	To validate MobiDataLab Results WP2 and WP3 To review datasets
Technical Workshop	Virtual/Brussels (tbc)	M20	To prepare challenges for living labs
Datathon	tbd	M20-M26	To participate in co-creation activities, providing challenges and answering participants' questions.
Hackathon	tbd	M26-M32	To participate in co-creation activities, providing challenges and answering participants' questions.
Codagon	tbd	M32-M36	To participate in co-creation activities, providing challenges and answering participants' questions.

The activity plan will be presented to the Reference Group in the kick-off meeting and is subject to changes. Reference Group members will be invited to participate in other MobiDataLab tasks and in consequence new activities may be included.

6.3. Virtual and Living Labs

Virtual (living) labs are becoming increasingly popular due to the variety of features they entail in combination with the context of their creation. For MobiDataLab, the purpose of the living lab is to create an ecosystem of mutually dependent components in the scope of an innovation ecosystem and an environment with early user involvement in real-time. The main objective is to leverage the technology and knowledge on data analytics and on data exploitation across countries thanks to the stimulation of Innovators (data users; SMEs & start-ups). They will be challenged to use various data sources and tools to sort out categories of major issues and problematic use cases introduced by Data Providers which facilitate their data assets and other stakeholders in the project's Reference Group. In the following sections, more details are provided.

6.3.1. Data Providers/Owners

Data providers have been engaged through the MobiDataLab Reference Group and will be asked to define their specific challenges (individual or cluster [aggregation of more than one data provider] oriented challenges). Data providers will be invited through the Reference Group to participate in Living Labs' sessions where Innovators present their solutions to solve the proposed challenges. They are involved in operating the labs, providing specific challenges related to the context of their municipalities, hosting sessions and participating in the use cases definition. They also participate in evaluation surveys.

6.3.2. Innovators (data users)

The Innovators will be entrepreneurs, hackers, developers, researchers, start-ups and SMEs that have the knowledge and skills to propose concepts that overcome the Data Providers' challenges. The challenges will be issued as an open call for entrepreneurs and promoted across the various ecosystems. F6S is much experienced in animating the innovator network, being the largest Startup/SME community globally, and will promote the MobiDataLab project using their communication channels to reach out to tech specialists.

6.3.3. Virtual and Living Labs tool for improving the culture of sharing data

MobiDataLab will develop a Virtual Lab consisting of an advanced User Interface that incorporates and digitalises functionalities referring to social and other features. The Virtual Lab will be the front face of the Transport Cloud and will allow different roles to connect and execute actions, either with the community (e.g., voting, reviewing, commenting) or with the cloud (e.g., data usage, API access, module upload). MobiDataLab will pilot the Transport Cloud through 3 Living Lab occurrences (a hackathon, a datathon and a "codagon", from English [code] and Greek [agon] meaning contest) in various times during the project's execution in order to increase interest for the cloud, test its functionalities and allow innovators to develop their solutions by using data and functionalities of the cloud. The Living Lab occurrences will invite participants to mostly physical locations and, in some cases, Virtual meetups and request from them to engage in co-creation, exploration, experimentation and evaluation activities in the scope of developing new tools and apps.

The first occurrence of the MobiDataLab's Living Labs is the **datathon**. The #datathon will invite participants to retrieve and utilise the data that are stored in MobiDataLab's cloud with the goal to find new usages for the data and additional insights from using them especially in fusion with other datasets (either stored in the cloud or elsewhere – only open sources).

The second occurrence of the MobiDataLab's Living Labs is the **hackathon** via a series of meetups. The #hackathon will request from participants to develop new data analytics tools built with the resources of the MobiDataLab cloud (data, APIs or software). The goal of the #hackathon is to generate usable technology based on the data and tools of the cloud.

The third instance of the MobiDataLab's Living Labs is the **codagon** (from English [code] and Greek [agon] meaning contest). The #codagon is a unique occurrence coined in MobiDataLab. It will utilise and validate the full range of MobiDataLab's technological artefacts' functionalities through a three-week-long event that will be executed remotely and physically (its last day will take place in a physical location). During the #codagon, participants will be requested to utilise the opinions of the community for progressing their work and to utilise the resources of MobiDataLab cloud.

With each x-athon, before their execution, a webinar will be organised to share information for each x-athon to interested participants. The webinar will be disseminated through MobiDataLab's channels and partners will help through their own organisation's channels.

A dedicated communication and stakeholder engagement plan will be designed in task 5.3 Planning and Monitoring of Living Labs (M14-36).

6.4. Events

The MobiDataLab project plans to organise its own online and face-to-face dissemination events, as well as take advantage of other established events, including those events organised by partners networks, beyond the events organised in the scope of the Virtual and Living Labs. Dissemination opportunities will also be sought at other relevant events, including those targeted at transport practitioners, researchers, policymakers and the startup community, among others.

All partners will contribute to the dissemination of the MobiDataLab results by publishing papers on selected conferences, attending workshops and events, and presenting the results in booths and relevant forum. This will be monitored by F6S through the creation of an "Events log", shared with project partners and regularly monitored in the internal project and WP6 meetings.

There are 2 types of events considered in the MobiDataLab dissemination strategy. Short videos and blog posts on the project's website may be developed presenting key moments, short testimonials or the recap of the events organised by the partners or by the partners' network. These are the following:

- **Internal events** – organisation of online and face-to-face dissemination events for providing tangible experiences on the project's results:
 - Organisation of, at least, 1 Webinar per year (3 in total) to communicate key findings of the project to relevant stakeholders.
 - Organisation of a final event by F6S (country still to be defined), with the support of all partners, to be held towards the end of the project to present MobiDataLab's main findings to relevant stakeholders.
- **External events:**
 - Presentation in, at least, 3 international scientific conferences, summits, workshops, and other relevant community events per year (9 in total), organised by or associated with partners or by other external entities (scouting or by invitation) including the Annual POLIS Conference, which attracts 500+ delegates from across the transport spectrum.

In Table 5, there is a non-exclusive list of the planned participation in events during the 1st year of MobiDataLab.

Table 5 Planned attendance to relevant events in the first 12 months

Name of event	City, Country	Date	Partner(s) attending	Main interest for MobiDataLab
42nd IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy	online	23-27/05/2021	URV	Present the MobiDataLab outcomes to computer security and privacy researchers
SOBIGDATA++ Awareness Panel	online	10/06/2021	AKKA	Keynote speaker at "Mobility data sharing: application potential and ethical issues" panel
State of the Map	online	09-11/07/2021	TBD	The annual international conference of OpenStreetMap
Privacy Enhancing Technologies Symposium (PETS 2021)	online	12-16/07/2021	URV	Present the MobiDataLab outcomes to computer security and privacy researchers
ITS World Congress	Hamburg, Germany	12-15/10/2021	ICOOR AKKA HERE POLIS	Engage with European/worldwide ITS community and promote the results and best practices in terms of data sharing. Develop new partnerships and create exploitation opportunities
MobiDataLab 1 st Webinar	online	Autumn/Winter 2021 (tbc)	All partners	1st Webinar organised by MobiDataLab to present the project, showcase initial results, and disseminate upcoming activities for the next year
POLIS Annual Conference	online	01/12/2021	POLIS	Engage with a large and diverse community of transport authorities (city/regional/national) and other transport domains

For organised, co-organised and external events, MobiDataLab partners will be asked to have a common approach regarding (i) pre-event promotion/communication campaigns, (ii) brand exposure, (iii) agenda and speakers, as well as (iv) partners participation, when possible.

- For organised events, which includes the Webinars and the final dissemination event, F6S platform will be used for registrations and F6S Zoom account will be used for streaming the events. Other platforms can be used for registration and streaming, if decided among partners. The communication campaign will be held on MobiDataLab's social media channels and partners will be asked to disseminate the event among their networks. Brand exposure should comply with the rules identified in sections 3 and 4 of this Report, namely on what concerns the use of the MobiDataLab logo and templates for presentation. All communication-related material, such as the event's webpage, agenda, leaflet, promotional printed material, etc., should always comply with the rules identified in sections 3 and 4 of this Report. The needs for each event will be identified on a case-by-case and presented by F6S to the remaining partners in WP6 meetings, for validation.
- For external events, participating partners are asked to use, when possible, the MobiDataLab template for presentation and, when relevant, to communicate to F6S, as task leader, and to POLIS, as WP leader, with 1 month in advance their participation in such events, providing the

official website page and an overview of the presentation so that this participation can also be promoted on MobiDataLab’s social media channels and website.

6.5. Cooperation Initiatives

MobiDataLab will seek to liaise thematically and establish synergies with other EU projects and initiatives from Horizon 2020 and beyond. This may result in collaborations such as the co-organisation of events, the involvements of representatives of such initiatives in the MobiDataLab project (and vice versa), sharing knowledge and best practices, and the cross-promotion of activities and results, for an increased outreach of the project outcomes. The project is expected to cooperate with, at least, 3 projects and initiatives per year (a total of 9) and a Partnership Agreement (PA) will be drafted by F6S for approval of project partners, to be signed with news partners to officially establish the cooperation.

For communication purposes, a MobiDataLab communication kit will be shared with the responsible person of these initiatives to ensure the use of the MobiDataLab visual identity. All collaboration opportunities will start with an exploitation meeting to identify common interests, and afterwards, should both parties agree, the PA will be signed. In MobiDataLab’s case, the Project Coordinator is expected to sign on behalf of the project.

The monitoring of this activity will be done by F6S, with the support of all project partners, and the involvement of further project partners in the cooperation process will be done on a case-by-case need, after the joint identification of the collaboration pathways between both parties. Project partners are thus asked to inform F6S, as task leader, and POLIS, as WP leader, of any potential collaboration, and provide the necessary content for scheduling an initial meeting and further developing the collaboration. A “Collaboration log” has been created, for regular monitor and reporting on the progress of cooperation initiatives. Also, a partnership page on the project’s website is being considered, in order to showcase the collaborations established and the work jointly developed.

Table 6 is a non-exclusive list of the projects and initiatives already identified by project partners and with which MobiDataLab will follow and/or establish cooperation during the 1st year of MobiDataLab.

Table 6 Identified potential collaborations with relevant initiatives in the first 12 months

Name of the initiative	Brief description	Main relevance for MobiDataLab
SoBigData++: European Integrated Infrastructure for Social Mining and Big Data Analytics (Horizon 2020)	Deliver a distributed, Pan-European, multi-disciplinary research infrastructure for big social data to understand the complexity of our society. SoBigData++ will produce tools and services to empower researchers and innovators through a platform of data and algorithms sharing	Exploit the results in terms of know-how on a platform for sharing datasets and analysis methods. This can be exploited in the Transport Cloud and Use Cases

SYN+AIR - Synergies between transport modes and Air transportation	SYN+AIR aims to develop common sets for data sharing between transport service providers (TSPs), enabling passengers to enjoy a seamless door-to-door travel experience	Build on the research results regarding the semantic enrichment activities. Specifically, on the new concept of multiple aspects trajectories methods, methods to manage these kinds of mobility data and analysis like for example prediction based on Machine Learning, similarity methods. This can be exploited in the Transport Cloud and Use Cases
Molière - MOBiLity sERVICES Enhanced by GALILEO & Blockchain	Molière will build the world's best open data commons for mobility services, the “Wikipedia of public transport and new mobility data”, a Mobility Data Marketplace (MDM) underpinned by blockchain technology, raising the profile, visibility, availability, and utility of geo-location data from GALILEO, and will test it to fuel and demonstrate a diverse set of concrete, highly relevant mobility scenarios and use cases where geo-location data is key, addressing the needs of cities, public transport authorities, mobility service providers, and end-users	Exploit the results in terms of know how on a platform for sharing datasets and analysis methods. This can be exploited in the Transport Cloud and Use Cases
REACH - EuRopEAn incubator for trusted and secure data value Chains (Horizon 2020)	The EU-funded REACH project will launch a sustainable European second-generation incubator for data-fuelled startups and SMEs with the aim of developing innovative experiments within data value chains. The project will issue three open calls, expecting to attract more than 500 data-driven concept applications and select 100 business ideas	Have access to a pool of data-driven startups and SMEs to engage within the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs
DMS Accelerator (Horizon 2020)	Supporting the European data market providing free support services to data-centric SMEs and startups	

6.6. Scientific Publications and Specialised Magazines

MobiDataLab will also aim at publishing articles and scientific papers in specialised media, magazines and journals. These will be means to target transport professionals and urban mobility practitioners, some examples: Thinking Cities, ELTIS, Cities Today, Talking Highways, Revolve, Intelligent Transport, EuroTransport, The International Journal of Urban Policy and Planning, IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, Transportation Science, European Data Protection Law Review IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, IEEE Transactions on Big Data, International Journal of Law and Information Technology, International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research, Knowledge and Information Systems, International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology, Journal of Transportation Engineering, EURO Journal on Transportation and Logistics, Research in Transportation Economics, among others.

Additionally, to make sure all peer-reviewed journal is openly accessible, MobiDataLab will publish the articles in the Open Research Europe platform.

7. Monitoring impacts

7.1. Monitoring table (KPIs)

This section establishes Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will help monitor the implementation of the Dissemination plan, some of these KPIs were established during the proposal stages. These KPIs will be collected and evaluated to monitor and enhance the performance and outreach of the project and that for online media, press coverage and events. The registration of the activities will be done right after these have taken place in the database that has been created for this purpose, the following section explains this registration procedure.

Table 7 MobiDataLab Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Activity	Expected performance		
	KPI target: Year 1	KPI target: Year 2	KPI target: Year 3
Website – number of visitors	≥200/month	≥300/month	≥500/month
Twitter – number of followers	75	150	200
Twitter – number of posts	50	100	200
LinkedIn – number of followers	75	150	200
Newsletter – number of newsletters sent out	1/year	1/year	1/year
POLIS newsletter – number of MobiDataLab articles	≥3	≥3	≥5

Technical leaflets: Published and distributed (online)	≥ 500	≥ 500	≥ 1000
Number of peer reviewed publications		≥2	≥2
Number of non-scientific publications	≥1	≥2	≥3
Number of final event attendees	-	-	100-150
Number of representations at events	≥3	≥3	≥3
Number of liaison activities organised	≥3	≥3	≥3
Number of participants in awareness events	≥20	20-50	20-50

7.2. Activity registers and dissemination procedure

Four dissemination registers (or logs) have been created in the project's sharepoint:

1. Events;
2. Cooperation activities (with other projects);
3. Dissemination activities (social media, news, press release, webinar/workshop participation, mass-media publication, video, website, etc.);
4. Publications (in scientific journals, repositories and/or magazines).

All activities for these categories should be recorded on a regular basis in these registers.

The participation of consortium partners in any event with an opportunity for dissemination and promotion of MobiDataLab (conferences, workshops, etc.), as well as the performance of every dissemination activity related to eCharge4Drivers (presentations, paper submissions, material distribution etc.), has to be communicated beforehand to F6S, POLIS and AKKA.

7.2.1. Step-by-step procedure

1. When an event opportunity is identified, please notify the dissemination management team (POLIS, F6S) of your intention at least 1 month in advance, specifying the details of the activity (type of activity, date, title, audience) and your role in it related to the MobiDataLab project (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, author, etc.). Prior notice is needed to update the Upcoming Events section of the MobiDataLab website and to allow cross-checking for overlaps and conflicts.
2. Register the activity in the Dissemination log with as many details as possible within 5 working days after the activity took place.

3. After your participation, send a short abstract (content of the session/presentation/discussion, quotes from speakers, highlights, pictures, relevant information related to MobiDataLab, size and type of audience reached) to POLIS top update the News section of the website.

The WP Leader(s), after consultation with the dissemination management team and in collaboration with the coordinator, can reject the proposed activity if it/they has/have objections related to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information concerning the work performed in the different WPs. In case of conflict, the dissemination management team and the involved partners will further discuss.

Conclusion

8.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan has identified and described the target groups for dissemination activities and highlighted how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It described the main dissemination tools, which will be particularly important for outreach activities. This strategy has also identified key initiatives and EU-funded projects to establish strategic alliances and collaboration mechanisms and defined the methodology for the establishment of the external interest groups that will play an important role in the transferability of the obtained results.

MobiDataLab consortium

The consortium of MobiDataLab consists of 10 partners with multidisciplinary and complementary competencies. This includes leading universities, networks and industry sector specialists.

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